

CHEMISTRY LEARNING SKILLS OF SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, ENGINEERING, AND MATHEMATICS STUDENTS: INFLUENTIAL ROLE OF TEACHERS' BLENDED EDUCATIONAL STRATEGY USAGE

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to explore the influence of blended educational strategies practiced by teachers on the chemistry learning skills of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) students. Surveying 100 STEM students from a private senior high school in Davao City, it was found that students perceived the level of blended educational strategies used by their teachers to be high, with an overall mean score of 4.08. Similarly, STEM students rated their chemistry learning skills high, with an overall mean score of 4.09. The Pearson Product Moment correlation statistical analysis revealed a significant moderate positive association between students' perceptions of blended educational strategies and their chemistry learning skills. Furthermore, it was discovered through simple linear regression analysis that teachers' blended educational strategies significantly predicted STEM students' chemistry learning skills. These findings underscore the importance of integrating blended educational approaches into STEM curricula to improve students' academic performance and overall learning experience in science, particularly in the blended learning environment.

Keywords: *Blended Education, Teaching Strategy, Chemistry, Learning Skills, Teachers, Davao City, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

As COVID-19 strikes, education all over the world has been altered and introduced to a different type of learning modality. As a result, limited face-to-face has been slowly implemented in different schools all over the globe. This face-to-face modality has been supported with digital learning modality also known as blended learning to ensure the continuous learning of the students even in a distance context. Yet, one of the difficult science subjects is chemistry. Students tend to feel uninterested in the subject matter because of some factors like their basic knowledge and/or the teacher's teaching strategies. Students find it extremely difficult to comprehend the microscopic/macrosopic chemical world and abstract notions in chemistry since they deal with difficult concepts like molecular structures, chemical bonds, and chemical reactions (Mazzuco et al., 2022). Given that chemistry is a difficult subject even in a normal face-to-face class, it gives more challenge to students to grasp the content independently during their online session. With this, students' learning skills in chemistry will be affected by how the teachers deliver the lessons during face-to-face and online learning sessions.

The huge advantages of cutting-edge digital technology in education have been realized since 2020 when the COVID-19 pandemic compelled all educational institutions to swiftly switch to online instruction to ensure students' continuous learning in an emergency circumstance appealing to additional educational support (Abuhassna et al., 2022). The effectiveness of online home learning is significantly impacted by teacher negligence, inadequate tools and infrastructure, and a lack of discipline and learner independence while implementing long-distance learning (Sunaryo et al., 2022). This effect will become more pronounced in science courses like chemistry, which students perceive to be challenging (Kartimi et al., 2021). The abstract, illogical, and particle nature of chemistry makes it challenging for students to comprehend its principles (Gafoor & Shilna, 2013). Numerous elements, including students' attitudes toward chemistry, motivation levels, learning resources, interpersonal interactions, collaboration, and students' irregular attendance in class, have been identified as contributing to the persistent low success in chemistry. However, because of the COVID-19 pandemic, there is little data on what influences students' success in chemistry during online and distance learning. The COVID-19 pandemic in the UAE made it important to look at a few measures of students' performance in online and remote chemistry lessons (AlMahdawi et al., 2021).

Meanwhile, as COVID-19 strikes in the Philippines, the government together with advocates for high-quality education and DepEd curriculum specialists opted to use blended learning strategies (Tupas & Linas-Laguda, 2020). There has been a growing demand for blended learning, and this possesses problems and challenges (Alvarez, 2020). Success in blending learning strategies in science necessitates a well-established information technology system. However, the Philippines' information technology structure is less developed than that of wealthy nations because it is a developing nation (Pagaran et al., 2022). Online lectures are not very common in most academic institutions in the Philippines and chemistry lectures are generally given in classroom settings (Lapitan et al., 2021), obviously, students will meet major challenges with it (Manila

Standard, 2021). However, in addition to the instructor aspect, other factors have also been demonstrated to have an impact on students' performance. Students' performance in science classes like chemistry was also found to be significantly influenced by student- and environment-related factors. Therefore, the daunting task of reawakening interest and creating an environment that is conducive to the effective teaching of chemistry in particular and the sciences in general falls on the shoulders of the chemistry teacher, students, parents, high school administrators, curriculum planners, and the government (Orbe 2018).

In a study conducted in Davao de Oro, distance learning is becoming the new norm, and its implementation makes students more anxious because they must individually learn and adjust to a particular learning style. This leads to a thorough investigation of student motivation and self-direction, particularly in distance learning. With regards to the science performance of Filipino students, they still have a shadow cast over their contribution to improvement, despite the current level of competence that the Filipino students earned from international exams like PISA and TIMSS. About 22% of students in the Philippines received a Level 2 or better in science. These students can correctly explain well-known scientific phenomena and use what they've learned to solve straightforward problems. Students' performance in science subject specifically in chemistry is affected by their attitude. The professors' favorable attitudes toward science had an impact on the students' positive attitude in their chemistry class (Rebucas & Dales, 2022).

According to Rebucas et al. (2022), students must develop these abilities for self-directed, disciplined, and lifelong learning on a global scale. The absence of self-directedness in science learning presents difficulties because it will inevitably lead to poor academic achievement, a diminished sense of responsibility, and a deficiency in learning abilities (Rebucas & Dales, 2022). Students that study science, face challenges in their major subjects. Additionally, a study conducted at the University of Mindanao, Digos College, presented that some college students weren't prepared for online learning due to learners' control, self-directed learning, and the effectiveness of online communication. As a result, training employs technology and concentrates on creating learning materials that can be correctly planned to motivate students and encourage teachers to learn. As a result, the current class is more likely to forget crucial ideas required for higher learning, but it also opens the door for teachers to create solutions that make things work and are feasible (Dequito, 2022).

Rationale of the Study

The researcher seeks to present the importance of conducting the study especially that educators need to be strengthened with new e-teaching techniques in order to keep up with the new normal trend (Şal & Göçen, 2022). Let it be known that strategies must be carefully chosen to match the learners' needs, interests, motivations, and qualities. An excellent teacher approaches teaching and learning in a way that is more likely to provide learning outcomes of a better caliber (Valdez & Bungihan 2019). This is the primary reason why the researcher is inspired to see the relationship between blended

educational strategies and learning skills in chemistry among STEM students. Since that chemistry is being recognized as a core subject in the school curriculum and therefore it become a crucial for the growth of a national educational system (Sivagami & Balamurugan, 2019). A study conducted by Ibrahim et al. (2022), that mastery of the three levels of chemistry representations—macroscopic, microscopic, and symbolic—is one of the issues students in this field frequently encounter.

Since chemistry subject is difficult to comprehend since they deal with difficult concepts and observe abstract notion (Mazzuco et al., 2022), chemistry as a discipline and students' capacity to learn the subject successfully depend on the ability to recognize chemistry learning issues and find ways to meaningfully address them (Salame et al., 2022). With the literature presented above, the researcher finds the importance of conducting the study. Moreover, there are scarcity of study conducted in the locality about the mentioned study specifically in chemistry subject.

This study seeks to present the relationship between blended educational strategies and chemistry learning skills of STEM students. Aside from that what domain from blended educational strategies significantly influences the chemistry learning skill of students. This study will guide the science teachers in preparation of learning strategies anchored with blended learning modality. This study will benefit the following: Department of Education, school administrators, science teachers, students, and future researchers.

Research Questions

The problem deals with the educational strategies of teachers bounded in blended learning modality and chemistry learning skills of STEM students. More specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of blended educational strategies as perceived by science students in terms of:
 - 1.1 student-centered learning;
 - 1.2 teacher-centered learning;
 - 1.3 active learning strategies; and
 - 1.4 passive learning strategies?

2. What is the level of chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students when analyzed in terms of:
 - 2.1 critical thinking skill;
 - 2.2 collaborative skill;
 - 2.3 creativity and innovation; and
 - 2.4 technology application?

3. Is there a significant relationship between blended educational strategies and chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students?
4. Is there a domain of blended educational strategies that significantly influences chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students?

Hypotheses

This research study has the following null hypotheses that will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H_{01} . There is no significant relationship between blended educational strategies and chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students.

H_{02} . There is no domain of blended educational strategies that significantly influence the chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students.

Review of Related Literature

Blended Educational Strategy

There are studies and reports presented a clear demand for improved science education, not only in the subject content but also in how teachers relay the information to the students (Ma et al., 2018, as cited by Mshayisa, 2022). This means that teaching delivery has a factor in the learning process of the students. Based on a study conducted, an effective teaching has an engaging classroom presence, contextualization of real-world skills, exchange of best practices and a lifelong love of teaching (Barrera & Dela Cerna, 2022). In the past two years of having full online learning caused by COVID-19 pandemic, the term blended learning idea is viewed as a strategy (Abuhassna et al., 2022). Moreover, education is adapting with the quick and ongoing innovation in educational technologies in this digital age. Blended learning is confidently emerging (Anthonysamy et al., 2020). Since in the early 2000s, a number of educators and scholars have defined the term “blended learning” (Tahir et al., 2022).

Blended learning is the integration of both face-to-face learning and online learning. It maximizes the advantages of both these teaching approach (Sukma & Priatna, 2021). In the application of blended learning, students and teachers are able to conduct their lesson during face-to-face and continue the learning process even in a distance using digital tools. Furthermore, the idea of blended learning is growing popularly among educators, curriculum designer, and particularly in students (Widjaja & Aslan, 2022). There are several studies have investigated the effect of blended learning on students' outcomes, as well as teachers' perception to blended models (Tahir et al., 2022). An

innovative approach to education is the blended learning technique, which combines in-person instruction with online learning. a skillfully executed blend of classroom instruction that takes place in person and online learning that can be accessed at any time. Due to the time constraints, ease of student boredom during the learning process, and requirements of increasingly pervasive technical innovations (Wardani et al., 2018).

In addition, online learning promotes independent learning for students. To support students' independent study, a variety of learning tools, including Google Classroom, Microsoft Teams, etc., have been developed (Supriyanto et al., 2020). Due to the availability of this learning platform, students can study independently at home utilizing digital materials created by their teachers and this learning platform (asynchronous learning). The learning process and evaluation will proceed as usual, just like in a traditional classroom, but integrating synchronous and asynchronous learning (blended learning) (Resta et al., 2020). The learning procedure is the only thing that has changed from the COVID-19 era, when all learning was done through an online system (distance learning) (Yulia, 2020).

The process of learning is collaborative. Critical components of students' motivation, success, and achievement include teacher-student interactions and student-student collaborations (Lagat & Concepcion, 2022). A study conducted in Thailand revealed that in the past, junior high school teachers in Thailand concentrated on the traditional teaching approach by imparting their expertise to students. Nevertheless, teachers have been urged to enhance student learning methods in lieu of knowledge transmission in light of changes to national policy. As a result, media has been used in educational institutions to motivate students. The majority of teachers, however, have focused on creating and innovating instructional methods rather than learning innovations that encourage students to learn for themselves and improve their ability to research knowledge from teacher-prepared media (Kwangmuang et al., 2020).

In the implementation of blended learning modality as teaching approach, there are some factors affecting the students' learning process. A study conducted by Lee and Recker (2021) that investigate which teaching approach led to the highest levels of student engagement in introductory online statistics or math courses, as well as how this approach affected participation and performance. The findings revealed four different factors that all had a favorable impact on students' performance: thorough feedback, problem-centered discussion settings, open-ended prompts, and grading. Additionally, students who attended sessions where the lecturers annotated their classmates' writings and encouraged in-depth discussion received final average marks that were considerably higher (Lee & Recker, 2021). Another relevant study that explored how factors at the course, student, and lecturer levels affected the distance learning performance of secondary school students enrolled in English language and literature courses. The results at the course level showed that students benefit more in classes that include project-based learning and deep learning activities. Additionally, findings from a student's perspective revealed that students perform better in class when they log in more frequently, stay longer, and refrain from enrolling in courses solely to earn credit (Zheng,

2020). The learning process of students is affected with the teaching approach done by the teacher.

Chemistry Learning Skills

Chemistry is a branch of science that investigates natural events, rules based on matter and structure, as well as the characteristics and energy changes connected to various material transformations (Neiles & Bowers 2020). According to Tekane et al. (2020, as cited by Dewi et al. 2021), chemistry learning attempts to comprehend chemistry topics because chemistry education is known as the principles of education and chemistry itself. Students, however, find it challenging to relate abstract chemical concepts to practical situations. The main goals of chemistry education research are to improve students' understanding of chemistry ideas and to foster meaningful chemistry learning. In order to assist students' grasp concepts and other learning variables, such as instruction and evaluation, it is often focused on learning methodologies and media (Dewi et al. 2021). The learning achievement in chemistry at the senior secondary school levels has been the subject of numerous research over the years. The results of these research showed that students struggled to understand some fundamental ideas, particularly those related to creating chemical formulas and equations and doing calculations from them, concepts of chemical reaction equilibrium, and mole concepts, among others (Musengimana et al., (2021).

According to studies on the learning of chemistry, students frequently think that learning chemistry in general particularly is challenging. In addition, any kind of explanation requires mutually accepted symbolic representations. Some authors contend that students view chemistry as an irrelevant subject that is uninteresting, divorced from reality, and of no interest for their future in addition to the cognitive difficulties to learning it. Moreover, due to the fact that chemistry "often involves numerous abstract concepts, which are fundamental to further learning in both chemistry and other disciplines," it is urgent to engage students in the topic and encourage their active involvement in learning (Araújo et al.,2022). In addition, the implementation of student-centered methodologies must be widely adopted in this situation, thus the chemistry education field must focus efforts in this direction. Due to the way these approaches apply theoretical ideas in practical situations, students have more freedom to study. This makes it easier for content to be related to reality, which can aid in comprehending (Bernardi et al., 2022).

The Queensland Curriculum and Assessment Authority (2015) defined 21st-century skills as "high priority abilities and qualities thought to be the most important in assisting students and learners in living and working successfully in the twenty-first century" (Maya & Suseno, 2022). Learning in the twenty-first century involves more than just teachers imparting information to students, it also involves helping them develop their knowledge and abilities to the fullest. They are anticipated to become more adaptable and competitive on a worldwide scale as a result of this optimization (Jumriani & Prasetyo, 2022). According to Hixson et al. (2012), stated that every learner in the twenty-first century should possess the following learning skills namely, critical thinking skills, collaborative skills, communication skills, creativity and innovation skills, and

technological application. Students can become conscious of their own learning requirements and choose how they want to acquire knowledge. In addition, rather than memorization, they may comprehend the nature of knowledge. Students who want personal improvement or higher education can meet their learning goals flexibly and freely through lifelong learning (Tekkol & Demirel, 2018).

Curriculum, teaching methods, assessment, and infrastructure all need to be up to date for chemistry education in the twenty-first century. Students must gain 21st century abilities, values, and attitudes in addition to their academic, interdisciplinary, and practical understanding of chemistry if they are to be successful in the rapidly changing modern world. Along with literacy (i.e., information, media, and technology) and life skills (i.e., adaptability, leadership, initiative, productivity, and social), 21st century skills also comprise the four "Learning Skills," i.e. critical thinking, teamwork, communication, and innovation. Students are actively engaged in understanding scientific topics through learning activities as part of science education. In addition to being understood as such, these four learning abilities must to be integrated into every topic in chemistry, just like literacy and numeracy are. Only then will our students be able to internalize these skills (Bakhshi & Rarh, 2022). Furthermore, the educational approach is intended to pique students' interest and provide them practice in creating a scientific inquiry process that will enable them to identify solutions to issues regarding scientific phenomena in their immediate environment (Tahya et al., 2022).

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The study is mainly guided by the Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory (1984) (Abdulwahed 2009, as cited by Ssekamate et al., 2022). According to Kolb's theory, learning is effective when a participant has a concrete experience with the subject matter, followed by observation of that experience and reflection on it, which results in the formation of abstract concepts (analysis) and generalizations (conclusions), which are then used to test hypotheses in subsequent situations, leading to new work experiences (Ssekamate et al., 2022). Applying this theory to the present study, it is anticipated that learning ability of the students in learning chemistry will be a concrete experience if the teacher contextualized the topic especially with the aid of technology as part of making blended learning strategy successful. Emerging the students to an experiential learning, it will lead into a concrete understanding and appreciation of the topic.

Supporting the above stated theory is RAT theory (Replacement, Amplification, & Transformation) by Dr. Joan Hughes in 1998. Technology replacement refers to as technology substitution of instructional practices, student learning processes, or subject objectives. Technology amplification refers to raising the effectiveness, productivity, and efficiency of teaching methods, student learning procedures, or content objectives. The term "technology transformation" describes how certain elements of curriculum, instruction, or learning are reinvented using new and creative technology (Maphosa & Bhebhe, 2019). Based on RAT theory, teachers can develop educational strategies incorporate with blended learning modality that will be utilized in the lesson preparation

and delivery. This theory will support the idea of technology integration especially in blended learning modality which implements face-to-face and online learning modality.

Another theory that would support the learning skills of students especially in learning chemistry is the constructivist theory of Lev Vigotsky and Jean Piaget. It seeks to foster personal growth through the social exchange of knowledge among the students, allowing for the collaborative exchange and construction of knowledge. As a result, learning is rooted in how students engage with the outside world, which is essential to grasping new concepts and their linkages in many contexts (Bernardi & Pazinato 2022). According to Wahyudiati (2022) learning chemistry that is anchored with this theory will allow the student to increase the constructive attitudes, knowledge, and experience. The students will be able to appreciate and grasp the idea and concept of the topics in chemistry.

Figure 1 depicts the conceptual framework of the study. As can be seen in Figure 1, the independent variable is the blended educational strategies with four indicators: student-centered learning, teacher-centered learning, active learning strategies, and passive learning strategies. On the other hand, the dependent variable is chemistry learning skills with four indicators: critical thinking skills, collaborative thinking skills, creativity and innovation, and technology application. The arrow placed between the two boxes where both independent and dependent variables are positioned individually signifies the assumed influence.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

METHODOLOGY

The research will apply the non-experimental quantitative research design which is used to gather and examine numerical data. Additionally, this study utilized a descriptive correlation approach. According to Sousa, et al. (2007, as cited by, Guido, et al., 2012), the quantitative approach is popular and, in principle, symbolizes the desire to guarantee results are exact, avoid analysis and interpretation distortions, and thus provide a margin of safety against interference between two variables. With descriptive research approach, it attempts to presents, analyzes, and interprets data in order to describe how current

problems are being solved (Erwanto 2022). In order to determine which variables are linked, correlation is used. Stangor et al. (2015) mentioned that the correlation study strategy is utilized to find relationships between variables. The above-mentioned research design is appropriate since in this study, there is no random assignment, control groups, or variable manipulation for data will purely rely on observation through the survey. This design will aid in describing the relationship of blended educational strategies and chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students.

Research Locale

This research study will investigate the educational environment of a private school located in Davao City, Philippines, focusing specifically on the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) students within the senior high school unit. The institution houses both basic and tertiary education departments, along with technical vocational education and training programs, situated in the Davao Region. STEM education, designed to prepare students for higher education and careers in STEM fields, is gaining traction, particularly with initiatives led by the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) Secretary Fortunato dela Peña. The study's emphasis on grade 12 STEM students, particularly in chemistry, aims to understand student perceptions and experiences within this academic discipline. The researcher's employment and teaching role within the senior high school unit provide a unique advantage for conducting this investigation, ensuring convenient access to participants and relevant insights into the educational context.

Research Respondents

This research will focus on one hundred grade 12 senior high school students enrolled in the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand, selected through simple random sampling. Utilizing 100 samples, the study aims to statistically analyze data to address its research question effectively. This study will use the specific characteristics using the following criteria: must be enrolled in one of DepEd accredited schools in the locality; must be grade 12 under science, technology, engineering, and mathematics strand; must be 18 years and above; must complete and submit the study consent with attached signature. Two questionnaires will be used: the adapted blended educational strategies questionnaire with 20 items and the adapted chemistry learning skills questionnaire with 18 items, both divided into specific parts. Exploratory factor analysis will be employed to assess the reliability of responses to each variable and its indicators.

The 5-point Likert scale will be used in the questionnaire given to the respondents, with indicated values to determine the overall responses of the respondents on various parameters.

Likert Scale for Interpreting Blended Educational Strategies

Mean Interval	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The blended learning strategy is always manifested in classroom setting.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The blended learning strategy is often manifested in classroom setting.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The blended learning strategy is not manifested in classroom setting.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The blended learning strategy is sometimes manifested in classroom setting.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The blended learning strategy is rarely manifested in classroom setting.

Likert Scale for Interpreting Chemistry Learning Skills

Mean Interval	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The students' chemistry learning skills is exhibited outstandingly.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The students' chemistry learning skills is exhibited highly satisfactory.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The students' chemistry learning skills is exhibited satisfactory.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The students' chemistry learning skills is exhibited poorly.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The students' chemistry learning skills is exhibited very poorly.

Data Gathering

The researcher will begin by obtaining permission from the administration of the affiliated institution to conduct the study, focusing on grade 12 STEM students. The survey questionnaire will undergo validation by three educational experts, incorporating their feedback for refinement. Pilot testing involving twenty teachers will ensure clarity and reliability of the questionnaire. Ethical review by an institutional research ethics committee will safeguard participants' rights and dignity, bolstering the study's legitimacy. Following endorsement from the researcher's graduate school, permission from the head of the senior high school unit will be secured. Informed consent will be obtained from respondents before distributing the survey via Google Forms, enabling automated data collection. Google Workspace will facilitate data organization, with statistical analysis conducted using appropriate software. The researcher, guided by a statistician, will interpret findings within the context of the literature review, formulating recommendations and conclusions. Subsequent submission to the Research Ethics Committee for approval to publish will ensure adherence to ethical standards, with reviewers scrutinizing data collection procedures and participant safety measures.

Data Analysis

In analyzing the result of this study, the researcher will use the following statistical tools:

Mean. The mean is determined by dividing the total number of values in the data set by the number of values in the data set (Laerd Statistics 2022). In this study, the result mean will be used to answer the first two questions stated in the statement of the problem. It will describe the level of blended educational strategies as perceived by STEM students and the level of chemistry learning skills of STEM students.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation of Coefficient. The Pearson's correlation coefficient, r , measures how far all of these data points are from the line of best fit that a Pearson's correlation seeks to draw across the data of two variables (Sreedevi, 2022). This statistical tool will help to determine the significant relationship of blended educational strategies and chemistry learning skills of STEM students.

Linear Regression Analysis. Linear regression is a statistical method that connects an independent (explanatory) variable to one or more dependent (dependent) variables. If there is a relationship between changes in the dependent variable and changes in one or more of the explanatory variables (Haciibrahimoglu 2022). This regression analysis will be used to determine the specific indicators of blended educational strategies that significantly affect the level of chemistry learning skills among STEM students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section present, analyze, from the conducted empirical study which explored the blended educational strategies of teachers and chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) students.

Table 1. Level of Perceived Blended Educational Strategies of Teachers

Domain	Mean	Descriptive level
Teacher-centered	4.30	Very High
Passive Learning Strategies	4.21	Very High
Student-centered	4.09	High
Active Learning Strategies	3.73	High
OVERALL	4.08	High

Level of Blended Educational Strategies of Teachers

The first statement of the problem in this study is to determine the level of blended educational strategies as perceived by science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) students. Table 1 provides the answer of this objective.

The level of blended educational strategies of teachers in terms of teacher-centered, student-centered, passive learning strategies, and active learning strategies is presented in Table 1. Specifically, among these four indicators in blended educational strategies, teacher-centered is the highest domain which obtained a mean of 4.30 which descriptively interpreted as very high. This suggest that teacher-centered strategy is always manifested in blended educational strategies among teachers as perceived by STEM students in classroom setting.

This implies that in a very difficult subject like chemistry, teacher can assume and take on a major role in instructional design and delivery of the lesson, which can result into an improved control over the course content of the subject. This strategy is effective especially in delivering difficult content in chemistry. Additionally, teacher's guidance it promotes student independence in their learning. Moreover, teacher-centered strategy of teachers in teaching chemistry is essential for convenient learning among STEM students.

The result is in line and supports the findings of Wong et al. (2020), that students prefer the teacher-centered strategy to engage them in different learning environments. Providing teacher-centered approach among STEM students, it was emphasized in the study of Dervić et al. (2018), that teacher-centered approach emphasize direct instructions, lectures, and demonstrations may be more effective than student-centered ones, which allows students to engage in self-paced learning. Additionally, when it comes to enabling science learning and generating positive attitudes, computer assisted learning can be effectively delivered through teacher-directed approach than the student-directed approach.

The second highest domain is passive learning with a calculated mean score of 4.21 with a very high descriptive level. This indicates that passive learning strategy is always manifested in blended learning strategy among teachers as perceived by STEM students in classroom setting.

This implies that passive learning strategies on blended learning in learning chemistry provides a better transmission of knowledge for the students to understand the lesson since chemistry subject needs to be thoroughly discuss to the students for them to grasp the lesson. It also prevents misconception about the information needed to understand by the students. Additionally, it allows the student to focus within the context of the discussion and narrow down the information based on logical inference. Moreover, it allows the students to received information that are difficult to understand through thorough discussion by the teacher.

According to Maia (2023), which is in line with the result, discuss that passive lectures involve the teacher actively transmitting theoretical information to the students, who perform a (primarily) passive role by listening, annotating, and accepting the information offered by the teacher. Moreover, according to Rodriguez (2020), passive

learning allows students to enhance their defining, describing, listening, and writing skills. It also develops convergent thinking, which is often assessed by quizzes, assessments, and handouts.

The third highest domain is student-centered approach which obtain a mean of 4.09 which descriptively interpret as high. This suggest that student-centered strategy is often manifested in blended learning strategy among teachers as perceived by STEM students in classroom setting.

This result implies that student-centered approach in blended learning system has a broad ramification that enhance learning results. Students become active agents in their own learning when student engagement, motivation, and active participation are prioritized especially in learning chemistry. This learning approach encourages the improvement of problem-solving and critical thinking abilities as well as specific learning experience as it is applied in blended learning approach which enhances their learning outcomes.

The result is in line and supported with the findings of Cummings (2017), that encouraging student into learning engagement through active learning activities and assessments will lead into the development of their comprehension, retention, and problem-solving skills. It was also stated by Shrivastava and Shrivastava (2022) that student-centered blended learning, which uses information technology enable students to access learning resources and materials at any time, from any location, with anyone, is the future of the subsequent normal education paradigm.

The lowest domain among blended educational strategies is active learning strategy which obtain the mean of 3.75 with high descriptive level. Despite of having the lowest calculated mean, active learning strategy can often be manifested in blended learning strategy among teachers as perceived by STEM students.

This indicates that active learning strategy ca result into increasing student engagement and achievement. Critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and a change toward student-centered learning can all be supported by active learning practices that put students at the center of the learning process. These strategies can be supported in a mixed learning setting by online collaborative tools, adaptive learning technology, and individualized learning pathways.

The result of the study is aligned to what is presented by Such (2022), the progress to blended education for active learning in undergraduate science education is still in its early stage. It is also cited by Vodovozov et al. (2022), that active learning promotes students to take control of their own learning by creating their own knowledge through experience, while teachers support learning by making it real, engaging, and relevant. As a result, its significance is growing quickly.

The overall mean of blended educational strategies of teachers is 4.08 and interpret as high descriptive level which means blended educational strategies is often manifested among science teacher as perceived by STEM students in their chemistry class. High blended educational strategies by teachers can have a number of positive impacts on the learning and accomplishment of students.

This result has a significant implication that blended learning can help to keep students engaged, motivated, and successful by offering them a range of learning activities, tailored learning opportunities, and increased communication with teachers. Additionally, blended learning can provide students more freedom, save money, and improve teamwork. However, there are several challenges to implementing high integrated educational ideas into practice, such as the requirement for teacher preparation, sufficient funding, and family support. Despite these difficulties, blended learning is still a viable investment for schools due to its potential advantages.

The result corroborates the claim of Sharma and Shree (2023), which stated that upon their study the effects of various forms of education, such as online, F2F, and blended, on education in post-pandemic contexts within higher education. They discovered that blended education has much higher levels of facilitation than online and face-to-face instruction (e.g., program structure, active involvement, and feedback). In comparison to online and face-to-face learning, students said it was simpler to follow blended education courses, and they thought it provided an effective learning environment. Furthermore, the use of blended learning can have several advantages, including more learner flexibility, consolidated content, and chances to apply knowledge in practical situations (Tahir et al. 2022).

Level of Chemistry Learning Skills of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Students

The second statement of the problem in this study is to determine the level of chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students.

Table 2. Summary of the Level of Chemistry Learning Skills of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Students

Chemistry Learning Skills Domains	Mean	Descriptive Level
Critical Thinking Skills	3.74	High
Collaborative Skills	3.82	High
Creativity and Innovation	3.75	High
Technology Application	3.91	High
Overall	3.74	High

Level of chemistry learning skills of STEM students in terms of; critical thinking skills; collaborative skills; creative and innovation; and technology application. Table 2 presents the learning skills of STEM students in learning chemistry. Among the domains mentioned above, technology application has the highest calculated average mean of 3.91 which has a high descriptive level. This means that technology application is exhibited highly satisfactory in students' learning skills in chemistry topics since it is incorporated with blended learning.

This result implies that individual student needs and learning preferences are catered through personalized and adaptive learning platforms, which encourage a customized educational experience. The availability of enormous online databases and

resources encourages independent inquiry and critical thinking abilities among students. Additionally, it is evident that the application of technology in learning process assist the students to better understand concepts in chemistry through various learning materials.

This result is in line with the study of Osman and Lee (2014) stating that providing students visual examples of chemical processes at the macroscopic, microscopic, and symbolic levels, multimedia can aid in their understanding of abstract chemistry ideas. Furthermore, through these interactive visual aids, digital tools can enhance in students' conceptual understanding. For instance, virtual laboratory animations can bridge the gap between the macro and micro worlds by assisting students in seeing atoms, ions, and molecules at the sub-microscopic level. (Herga et al., 2016).

The second domains that has the highest average mean of 3.82 is collaborative learning which descriptively interpreted as high. This suggest that collaborative learning skills is exhibited highly satisfactory since learning chemistry is effective through peer collaboration and interaction given that chemistry concept is difficult and needs to be actively discussed within the classroom.

This result implies that students gain a greater knowledge of chemical principles through peer interaction, active participation, and discussion of ideas while working on projects. The variety of viewpoints encourages innovation and critical thinking, while also fostering successful teamwork and communication. Moreover, collaborative learning promotes interactive discussion with the teachers and their classmates to have an effective exchange of ideas to better understand the topics in chemistry.

The result supports the study of Fakomogbon and Bolaji (2020) that teachers are equipped with collaborative teaching strategies to use collaborative learning as a strategy to facilitate learning and enhance student performance. Chemistry instruction and learning methodologies must enable students to interact, share knowledge, and develop their comprehension and problem-solving abilities. The collaborative learning technique is thus one of the greatest methods for teaching chemistry (Niyonsaba 2022).

The third highest among the domains is creativity and innovation which obtain an average mean of 3.75 with a high descriptive level. This suggest that student's creativity and innovation skills are exhibited highly satisfactory.

This result implies that students are independent during their class discussions. It is evident that when the teacher allows their students to establish their own learning style, they will be able to retain and understand the topic being discussed. Fostering creativity and innovation in chemistry learning has far-reaching implications for students' growth and development. Additionally, student's ability to venture their imaginative skills will help them foster their chemistry learning techniques.

The findings has been supported by the study of Tatli and Ayas (2013) that learning chemistry with the aid of a virtual laboratory may improve students' motivation and achievement in learning as well as obtaining chemicals and laboratory apparatus for the experiment. Exercises that encourage creative problem-solving might enhance students' chemistry learning skills. Additionally, the application of laboratory-based critical and

creative thinking has a major impact on the development of creative thinking skills (Nuswowati & Taufiq 2015).

The lowest domain among chemistry learning skills of STEM students is critical thinking skills with an average mean of 3.74 which indicate with high descriptive level. Even though having the lowest among all other indicators, critical thinking skill is exhibited highly satisfactory among student's chemistry learning skills.

This implies that showcasing critical thinking skills among students allows them to analyze complex chemical problems, use deductive methods of understanding the chemical concept, and apply appropriate problem-solving skills. Having critical thinking skills among students helps them to widen their understanding about the concepts in chemistry which are very difficult to comprehend. Furthermore, it influences the learning process of the students resulting into an abstract reasoning.

In line with this result, a study of Utami et al. (2017) that students who possess critical thinking abilities are better able to reason through problems, draw conclusions, synthesize information, and evaluate situations both in and outside of the classroom. It is essential for academic success, especially in learning scientific concepts in chemistry and other fields of science. Critical thinking and chemistry are two qualities that go hand in hand. Students who study chemistry can improve their critical thinking abilities, while those who study critical thinking can benefit from studying chemistry (Siahaan 2021).

The overall mean average of chemistry learning skills of STEM students is 3.74 which indicates with high descriptive level. This means that the students' chemistry learning skills are exhibited highly satisfactory. It describes that the chemistry learning skills among STEM students are evident in the classroom set-up during blended learning sessions.

This implies that STEM students are highly equipped with a set of skills that is designed to participate and perform advanced chemistry topics in senior high school. Higher chemistry topics are more complex and complicated which widens the opportunity for the students to venture and delve into the topics. Anchored with blended learning strategies of teacher, students were able to actively participate in every blended learning activity prepared by the teacher.

The findings is supported by the study of Stanley (2022), the development of chemistry learning tools based on blended learning paradigms that foster students' of critical thinking skills in their learning experience. Additionally, according to the study of Hadisaputra, et al. (2020), that implementing blended learning in chemistry education can result in enhancements to students' achievement, metacognitive abilities, and self-efficacy. This means that blended learning promotes independent learning opportunities for the students in their learning skills on chemistry subject. (Supriyanto et al., 2020).

Significant Relationship between Blended Educational Strategies and Chemistry Learning Skills of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Students

The third statement of the problem in this study is to determine the significant relationship between blended educational strategies and chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students. Presented in table 3 the correlation coefficient, p value, decision on the hypothesis at a 0.01 level of significance, and with the statistical interpretation.

Table 3. Significance on the Relationship of Percieved Blended Educational Strategy Usage of Teachers and Chemistry Learning Skills of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Students

CHEMISTRY LEARNING SKILLS				
BLENDED EDUCATIONAL STRATEGY USAGE	r	p-value	Decision on H₀	Interpretation
	.514	.000	Reject	Significant

Table 3 depict the significant relationship between the Blended Educational Strategy Usage of Teachers and Chemistry Learning Skills of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Students and exhibited their relationship in the result. With an overall p-value of 0.000, the correlation is significant at a 0.01 level of significance. Thus, rejecting the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is the finding of this study which strengthen the relationship of two variables. The correlation coefficient of $r = 0.514$ shows a significant and moderate positive correlation between blended educational strategy usage of teachers and chemistry learning skills of STEM students.

The implication of this findings presents the interconnectedness of teaching strategies prepared by the teachers during online and face-to-face classes to the chemistry learning skills of STEM students. The significant positive correlation between blended educational strategy usage of teacher and chemistry learning skills of STEM students suggest that diverse blended learning strategies of teachers to address the different needs of students has a meaningful impact on the learning skills of STEM students especially in learning chemistry topics. This implies that blended learning is effective among STEM students in learning chemistry since students are also computer literate which also allow them to collaboratively work with their classmates.

Significant Influence of Perceived Blended Educational Strategy Usage of Teachers on the Chemistry Learning Skills of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Students

The fourth statement of the problem in this study is to determine a domain of blended educational strategies that significantly influences chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students. Presented in Table 4 the

data on which perceived blended educational strategy of teachers' domain has more influence to chemistry learning skill of STEM students.

Table 4. Significant Influence of Perceived Blended Educational Strategy Usage of Teachers on the Chemistry Learning Skills of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Students

Chemistry Learning Skills	Perceived Blended Educational Strategy Usage of Teachers						Decision on H_02 at α 0.05 level of significance	Interpretation
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients					
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.			
Constant	1.221	.357		3.418	.001			
Chemistry Learning Skills	.565	.095	.514	5.926	.000	Reject H_02	Significant Predictor	

R = 0.514; R² = 0.264; F-value = 35.123; p-value = 0.000

The regression analysis reveals a significant influence of the perceived blended educational strategy usage of teachers on the chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) students, as demonstrated by the unstandardized coefficient (B = 0.565) and the standardized coefficient (Beta = 0.514), both of which are statistically significant (t = 5.926, Sig. = 0.000). The rejection of the null hypothesis (H_02) at the α 0.05 level of significance confirms that the perceived blended educational strategy usage is a significant predictor of chemistry learning skills among STEM students. This indicates that students who perceive a higher usage of blended educational strategies by their teachers tend to exhibit enhanced chemistry learning skills.

Examining the overall regression model, the collective impact of the perceived blended educational strategy usage on chemistry learning skills is evident. The model's overall significance is reflected in an R of 0.514, denoting a strong positive correlation between teachers' perceived blended educational strategy usage and students' chemistry learning skills. The R² value of 0.264 suggests that approximately 26.4% of the variance in chemistry learning skills is explained by the perceived blended educational strategy usage. The F-value of 35.123, coupled with a p-value of 0.000, underscores the statistical strength of the model. This implies that, collectively, the perceived blended educational strategy usage significantly contributes to the overall chemistry learning skills of STEM students.

The implication of these findings emphasizes the importance of educators' utilization of blended educational strategies in enhancing students' chemistry learning skills. The significant positive relationship between teachers' perceived blended educational strategy usage and students' learning outcomes highlights the potential of incorporating diverse instructional approaches. This suggests that educators who integrate traditional and online teaching methods can positively impact students' mastery

of chemistry concepts. Educational institutions may consider providing training and support for teachers to effectively implement blended strategies, thereby fostering an enriched learning environment for STEM students.

Conclusions

The data gathered from the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics students draws the following conclusions:

The level of blended educational strategy usage of teachers as perceived by the STEM students is high. This indicates that the blended educational strategy of teachers provides a wide range of opportunities for the STEM students in learning chemistry. The teaching strategies prepared by the teacher which incorporate technology also allow the students to participate well in every discussion and activity.

The level of chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students is high. This indicates that the chemistry learning skills of STEM students allow them to productively perform in online and on-site discussions. STEM students effectively apply learning skills which enhance their scientific understanding and attitude in learning chemistry.

The perceived blended educational strategy usage of teachers and chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students shows a strong significant relationship. This indicates that various blended learning strategies of teachers contribute to the learning process skills of STEM students in chemistry subject.

Perceived blended educational strategy usage of teacher influence the effective chemistry learning skills of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students. The findings indicate that blended educational strategies of teachers tend to enhance the chemistry learning skills of the STEM students which significantly contributes to the overall chemistry learning skills of STEM students.

Recommendations

Department of Education. Based on the significant relationship of perceived blended educational strategy usage of teachers and chemistry learning skills of STEM students, it is recommended that Department of Education must provide professional development programs for the teachers especially in technological integration in teaching chemistry. This will allow the teachers to effectively integrate technology in their teaching process that will aid them in teaching chemistry during online and face-to-face activities.

School Administration. School administration should collaboratively communicate with the teachers to strengthen the teaching competence in integrating technology as part of the teaching process in chemistry subject. This can be achieved by providing support and resources such as technological equipment that can be used in blended learning approach.

Science Teacher. Science teachers should continue to actively participate in any professional development such as training and seminars in the usage of technology in education. This will allow them to widen their understanding on the usage of technology in integrating in formulating teaching strategies for STEM students. Moreover, science teachers must be innovative in implementing student-centered and active learning strategies that promote critical thinking skills, collaborative skills, and technological application.

Students. Students should equip themselves with technological knowledge and application to effectively participate in blended educational settings. Additionally, students should be provided with access to the basic technologies that are essential in their academic success.

Future Researcher. Future researchers can explore other educational strategies that enhance the chemistry learning skills of STEM students. They can conduct longitudinal study design to monitor shifts over time in both student learning results and teacher practices.

Overall, it is recommended that all stakeholders in the field of education should work collaboratively to provide an effective educational approach in blended learning. Continuous improvement and sustainable support programs are essential to ensure a high-quality of learning that will be received by the students that will allow them to become scientifically competent.

Ethical Considerations

The research emphasizes the importance of ethics in scientific inquiry, acknowledging the necessity of adhering to ethical norms throughout the research process. It underscores several key moral principles, including social value, informed consent, risk assessment, benefits, safety, privacy, confidentiality, justice, transparency, researcher qualification, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement. The study examines the transition to blended learning in educational institutions due to the COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on students' chemistry learning skills. It emphasizes the importance of obtaining informed consent from participants, ensuring their understanding of the research's purpose, risks, and benefits. Privacy and confidentiality are maintained through the use of secure data collection methods and the protection of respondents' personal information. The researcher's qualifications and commitment to ethical conduct are highlighted, as well as the involvement of the community in the research process. Through transparency and community engagement, the study aims to contribute to the advancement of knowledge while upholding ethical standards and respecting participants' rights.

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